

FNS – Cloud

Food Nutrition Security

Food Nutrition Security Cloud

Deliverable 6.4

Portfolio of communications resources

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Main contact:	Siân Astley (sa@eurofir.org)

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Version/Date	Change/Comment
2021-05-01 v1	<i>Plan with Outline</i>
2021-06-09 v2	<i>COO Comments</i>
2021-06-24 v3	<i>Final</i>
2021-06-30 1.0	<i>COO check</i>

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1 Publishable Summary

Existing food including agriculture, nutrition and security (FNS) data including knowledge and tools for health and agri-food sciences are fragmented, lack critical mass, and access by user communities is 'unevenly' distributed, meaning data are not readily re-used and existing services focus on clinical, molecular or biological sciences not FNS resources. Thus, the purpose of FNS-Cloud is to launch a first-generation food cloud, federating existing and emerging datasets, with intent to make FNS resources FAIRer, and develop new services to support users in their exploitation to benefit stakeholders.

Priorities for 2020 were, therefore, a project logo and branding (Sections 3.1 & 3.2), Office templates for the Consortium (Section 3.2), content for the FNS-Cloud project (Section 3.3), Community of Practice, and FNS Cloud websites (both pending at M6), Social Media content (Section 3.4), dissemination templates (Section 3.4), infogram, fact sheet, poster and banner (pending), and news items (Section 3.5). Examples of these were presented in the D6.1 and were available for Beneficiaries to download, as required.

Since D6.1 was submitted (M6), FNS-Cloud branding has been extended to include the Community of Practice (myFNSCloud) and the FNS Cloud websites, items (e.g., news) and pages (e.g., External Expert Advisory Board) have been added to the project website, and content generated for myFNSCloud. The scientific PowerPoint describing FNS-Cloud activities has been updated/ revised and a one-pager summary published in place of an infogram and fact sheet as well as certificates for event participation. Cooperation with Blue-Cloud has also expanded with the exchange of fish and seafood data and more information about this activity has been published online.

Priorities for Period 2 include substantial revision of the website, based on Period 1 activities and outputs, linking the project website to myFNSCloud (2021) and FNS Cloud (2022), capture and publication of event materials on the project website, and increased FNS-Cloud-specific social media content as well as continued collaboration with Blue-Cloud and, potentially, the European Open Science Cloud.

2 Introduction: Communications Resources

D6.3 Dissemination and Community Engagement Plan (DCEP) updated messages, tools and channels for FNS-Cloud dissemination, communication, and stakeholder engagement for Periods 2 and 3. This Deliverable, *D6.4 Portfolio of communications resources*, focuses on the tools generated to date (31.05.2021) for use by the Beneficiaries, generally, and WP6 specifically.

Whilst there are four FNS-Cloud scientific and technical objectives, the objectives of D6.3 DCEP and supporting materials described in this Deliverable are to:

- **Build relationships:** Create goodwill and awareness by being inclusive, informative and interesting
- **Inform:** Provide information for stakeholders to facilitate decision-making (e.g., how to access data)
- **Persuade:** Encourage user communities to engage with FNS-Cloud and overcome any reluctance especially around FAIRification of FNS datasets
- **Request:** Ask for action by or response from recipients (e.g. provide feedback)

Generic tools, such as corporate identity (logo, branding), were developed during M1-6 and have been extended to the Community of Practice (myFNSCloud) and FNS Cloud (cloud solution) during M7-M18. Similarly, the FNS-Cloud website was launched (M3), but planning, revising, and delivery is ongoing.

D6.3 DCEP and D6.4 Portfolio will be reviewed at Month 38, considering communication-related strengths and the development and progress of FNS-Cloud, but also the wider communications landscape, which has been impacted significantly by corona virus/ covid-19 public health restrictions globally.

Although Work Package (6) is led by EuroFIR, all Beneficiaries are involved in the activities, sharing information with networks and/ or participating in events. Also, as agreed during Period 1, FNS-Cloud aims to collaborate with Blue-Cloud whenever possible, whether related to data sharing or dissemination; latterly this has seen sharing of fish and seafood data from FNS-Cloud (EuroFIR) with Blue-Cloud and a joint publication describing this cooperation and the benefits for both projects.

3. Portfolio

3.1 Project branding

A project logo was developed as part of the wider branding of FNS-Cloud and is available in a variety of formats and file types and will be included in all project materials (M1-M6).

The logo font is Nexa and this font family has also been used for the website and project materials.

The Nexa family includes 16 unique font styles and weights - eight uprights with eight italics - and is characterised by legibility in both web and print design (sans serif), well-finished geometric designs, and optimised kerning etc. Nexa is suitable for most headlines of all sizes as well as for text blocks that come in both maximum and minimum variations. The font styles are applicable for any type of graphic design. However, this font is not available to most Beneficiaries, so the default font for Office documents is Calibri, also a sans-serif typeface family, which is available free in most software, e.g., Office 365.

The default colour for FNS-Cloud is Pantone 3272C (#00A19A) and three contrasting colours have been identified to ensure variety and interest (#1F2837 – navy; #ECECEC – grey; #EC6D64 – coral).

The fonts and style guide can be downloaded by Beneficiaries from the FNS-Cloud intranet.

	Main logo	Horizontal logo
Main logo		
Logo on a coloured background		
Black and white logo		

Subsequently, branding was developed for the WP7 Community of Practice (myFNSCloud) including a dedicated family of logos, which are also available for download (M6-M18).

	Main logo	Horizontal logo
Main logo		
Logo on a coloured background		
Black and white logo		

3.2 Beneficiaries branding

Beneficiaries’ logos (below) can be downloaded by Beneficiaries from the FNS-Cloud intranet.

These logos have been collected to ensure fair representation of the Beneficiaries on FNS-Cloud resources and to facilitate access by other Beneficiaries, particularly those in WP6. However, Beneficiaries should respect other Parties’ copyright and reputation in their use, meaning logos should be used correctly and not without notification. All copy should be sent to Beneficiaries’ representatives prior to publication.

3.2 Templates

Office templates have been developed for use internally and externally, specifically PowerPoint (simple and design), Word document, notification of dissemination and communication activities, and Deliverables. Beneficiaries should any additional branding (e.g. logo) in accordance with local rules.

These templates can be downloaded by Beneficiaries from the FNS-Cloud intranet.

<p>Document template (Word)</p>	
<p>Deliverable template (Word)</p>	
<p>Notification to publish (peer-review article)</p>	

3.3 Websites

3.3.1 FNS-Cloud, Project website

The FNS-Cloud project website – www.fns-cloud.eu – was launched on 31st December 2019 (M3) and includes a Homepage, Overview (including Consortium and Executive Board), Outputs (including Publications, [Public] Deliverables, Education [including Workshops, Work-based Learning, Community of Practice], Media, News, Events and Contact (M1-M6).

Subsequently, pages have been added for the External Expert Advisory Board Members (<https://www.fns-cloud.eu/overview/advisory-board>) and the Twitter feed added to News (<https://www.fns-cloud.eu/news>) as well as items to Overview (one-page summary), Events, and News (M6-M18). Pages describing the cookies policy, copyright, disclaimers, privacy, and terms and conditions were also updated.

Over the next few months (M18-M24), the project website will undergo a series of revisions, so the outputs of the project can be presented, based on Period 1 Reporting.

3.3.2 myFNSCloud, Community of Practice website

The WP7 Community of Practice (myFNSCloud) website – www.myfnscloud.eu – was launched on 30th June 2020 (M9) and includes a Homepage, Members (address book, map, rooms), Events (list, calendar, MyEvents), Forum, Blogs, Opportunities, Repository, and Partners (linked to the project website, Beneficiaries). Currently, the homepage is linked to the FNS-Cloud project Twitter feed (@FNSCloudEU), but this can be switched to the social media reserved for myFNSCloud in the future (see 3.4 Social Media).

Over the next few months (M18-M24), myFNSCloud will go public, inviting user communities to join and engage with FNS-Cloud. In anticipation, Google Analytics has been added to the site to monitor traffic.

3.3.3 FNS Cloud, Cloud solution landing page and catalogues

Currently, FNS Cloud – www.fnscloud.eu – is only available on a test platform but it includes the dataset and tools and services catalogues, which can be searched as well as the food map and links back to the project website and Community of Practice (myFNSCloud). These pages have been branded to match the project and myFNSCloud websites, supporting a seamless experience for user communities whilst still allowing the sites to be developed independently, as they have very different technical demands. There is a news section that, in future, will focus on news related directly to FNS Cloud rather than the project and Contact, which – ultimately – will lead to helpdesk services delivered by WP3 in partnership with WP6-7.

During the next Period (2), FNS Cloud will be developed further based on feedback from the first round of usability testing, before going live for testing amongst user communities.

FNS Cloud Landing Page	FNS Cloud Tools & Services Search Page

3.4 Social media

Planning and reporting of social media will be via a template posted on the FNS-Cloud intranet.

3.4.1 Twitter

Twitter accounts were set up for the project (@FNSCloudEU) and, in anticipation of the CoP, a second account has been created to work in parallel with www.myfnscloud.eu (@myFNSCloud) (M1M6).

Both are branded using the FNS-Cloud logo, acknowledge the funding source, and direct to the project website. Once the CoP is public, the @myFNSCloud account will direct to www.myfnscloud.eu.

During Period 1, content has focused on introducing the project or re-tweeting content from Beneficiaries, collaborators (Blue-Cloud), or user communities including EOSC, and have been in English, because the project was at a relatively early stage (M1-M18) and public health measures EU-wide meant fewer events.

Over the next few months (M18-M24), social media content will focus more on project outputs, based on Period 1 Reporting, and diversify content languages.

The aim will be to continue posting content 1-2 a week (minimum) up to 1-5 times a day (maximum) and to include images, which will exploit the greater likelihood of multiplication through re-tweets.

3.4.2 Instagram

Like Twitter, two Instagram accounts were created and branded, one for the project (@FNSCloudEU2019) and one for the CoP (@myFNSCloud). No effort was extended for these accounts during Period 1, but content based on Period 1 Reporting will be added during Period, focusing on images/ visualisation.

3.4.3 YouTube

The FNS-Cloud YouTube channel is being used primarily as a video hosting site to promote outputs, such as that presenting the kick-off meeting (13-14th November 2019, <https://bit.ly/3dIDrem>).

The next video anticipated for FNS-Cloud was a whiteboard animation, which time-lapsed drawings and narration to describe and explain a topic and will be hosted on YouTube and embedded on the website. However, because of the widespread shift to online events, FNS-Cloud will record public presentations (21st June 2021, ISEKI pre-conference symposium), unless uploaded to event sites in which case a link will be added to the project website, and post these for user communities to access at their convenience.

3.4 Factsheet, leaflets, posters, banners, etc.

A poster summarising FNS-Cloud was created for IEEE Big Data 2019 (9-12th December 2019 - Los Angeles, US) and a (draft) leaflet for the WP7 train-the-trainer programme was created for the EuroFIR Food Forum (7-9th April 2020 - Brussels, BE) and the M8 Consortium Meeting (3-5th June 2020 - Norwich, UK).

IEEE Big Data 2019	WP7 train-the-trainer programme
<p>Food Nutrition Security Cloud for Data Standardisation & Interoperability Changes</p> <p>INTRODUCTION Food and Nutrition Security Cloud (FNS-Cloud) started on 1st October 2019. This four-year EU-funded project aims to make food- and nutrition-related data FAIRer (Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable).</p> <p>OBJECTIVES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce fragmentation of existing governance models • Stimulate collaboration amongst FNS-domain researchers and ICT data specialists • Support a food systems approach to FNS research and innovation, focusing on use cases that address researchers' needs, especially in data intensive fields • Build on the progress of past projects, integrate existing communities, and make use of learning from parallel thematic initiatives developed under Horizon 2020 • Deploy global standards, advancing best practices for governance and financing <p>IMPLEMENTATION</p> <p>Technical Activities Evaluation</p> <p>Easy access to data via advanced user interfaces (for humans) and APIs (for machines)</p> <p>EOSC-compatible services for data standardisation and interoperability and knowledge extraction and data reuse</p> <p>Governance, business & finance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FNS-Cloud governance, business, and finance model(s) will be based on existing and emerging best practice • Open science and open innovation culture will be at the core of these frameworks as well as education and training. <p>DISCUSSION</p> <p>FNS-Cloud fills gaps in the current FNS landscape, since most food-, nutrition- and health-related research infrastructures focus on clinical, molecular or biological sciences.</p>	<p>FNS-Cloud Train-the-Trainer Making food nutrition security data FAIRer</p> <p>Do you use food nutrition security data? Do you generate food nutrition security (FNS) data? Do you want to contribute to making food and nutrition data FAIRer?</p> <p>FAIRer means Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. FNS-Cloud aims to federate new and existing FNS datasets, and train researchers in their further use.</p> <p>A train-the-trainer programme will begin in autumn 2020</p> <p>Your train-the-trainer programme will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ongoing (2020-2025), where trainers contribute to development of the programme content and methods • Part of a wider Community of Practice around FAIRer FNS data, knowledge, tools and FNS-Cloud Services • Action-based, interactive training • Mixture of hands-on and online modules • University accredited programme • Free-of-charge and open to all FNS-Cloud researchers <p>Education, Training & Support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train-the-trainer workshops • Katharine Flynn • Katharine.flynn@maastricht.ac.uk • Work-based learning • Loretta Hain • l.hain@maastricht.ac.uk • Community of Practice • Annemiek Pijl • a.pijl@maastricht.ac.uk <p>FNS - Cloud Food Nutrition Security Cloud</p> <p>Food Nutrition Security Cloud (FNS-Cloud) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020-EU-3.2.3.2.3 - A sustainable and competitive agri-food industry) under Grant Agreement No. 863059.</p> <p>education@fns-cloud.eu www.fns-cloud.eu</p>

A0 and A4 PowerPoint templates have been generated, which the Beneficiaries can use independently, to create materials as well as a PowerPoint (scientific) presentation (finalised M9, updated M18), summarising the project, which can be adapted by Beneficiaries or incorporated into other presentations.

ç	Scientific presentation

Based on this presentation, content for a one-page summary was agreed at the end of June 2020 and published in September 2020 (M12). Subsequently, it was revised (branding) and published online in M15.

These resources can be downloaded by Beneficiaries from the FNS-Cloud intranet.

One-page summary (P1)	One-page summary (P2)
<p>One-page summary (P2)</p> <p>The poster features the FNS-Cloud logo and title. It lists short-term (2025), medium-term (by 2030), and longer-term (2030 onwards) objectives. It includes a grid of partner logos such as EFOST, ENA, EuroFIR, FODCASE, lifely, RTDS, scalefocus, BfR, University of Reading, APRE, Maastricht University, dea, NUTRITIGS, and DTU. At the bottom, it states: "Food Nutrition Security Cloud (FNS-Cloud) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020-EU.3.2.2.3 - A sustainable and competitive agri-food industry) under Grant Agreement No. 863059".</p>	

Certificates for participation have also been generated (M18) and templates shared with WP7.

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FNS-Cloud Open Science Taster Workshop
14th April 2021

A certificate verifies that **Paul Finglas, Quadram Institute Bioscience (UK)**, participated successfully in the 90-minute FNS-Cloud course, as indicated.

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3.5 Newsletters and press releases

FNS-Cloud will not publish regular newsletters but will, instead, send concise tailored new items via MailChimp for internal and external stakeholders. These shorter, more frequent email updates are a better approach for volumes of information and time-critical content and can be monitored more effectively to understand what is being read, when, and the potential impact content is having.

The aim (M1-M18) was to publish news items at least once a quarter to ensure content was current but did not overwhelm recipients. Content has included news (e.g., open calls for work-based learning) and requests for help (e.g., user feedback). However, in practice, a range of channels are being used to communicate with beneficiaries, because firewalls and spam filters remove

communications at source or individuals do not update safe addresses.

As the same issues will be encountered with stakeholders, a range of channels are being used including email (direct and marketing [e.g., MailChimp]), website and social media, and beneficiaries' networks.

The first press release will be published summarising Period 1 activities following the EC review (M20).

4. Conclusions

As a dynamic and on-going process, the portfolio of resources for the Consortium and deployed for dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement will be reviewed again in Months 38, considering communication-related strengths (i.e., what has been successful, impact) using the KPIs described in D6.3 DCEP and against the development and progress of FNS-Cloud.

Although Work Package (6) is led by EuroFIR, all FNS-Cloud Beneficiaries are involved, both in terms of achieving consensus (e.g., content for outputs) as well as demand-led creation of materials.

Blue-Cloud and FNS-Cloud continue to cooperate on dissemination with the latest publication being uploaded on 31st May 2021 (<https://bit.ly/2T5enIC>).